

Influence of Personality Related Stress on Student Athletes' Track Performance in Secondary Schools in Nakuru County, Kenya

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Abstract

The main purpose of this study was to analyze influence of Personality Related Stress on Student Athletes' Track Performance in Secondary Schools in Nakuru County, Kenya. The study adopted an ex-post facto research design targeting 3,584 form two and three students in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya. A sample of 351 students was drawn using purposive and stratified random sampling. Data was collected through structured self-administered questionnaires. Hypothesis was tested using regression analysis of .05 level of significance. Data was analyzed by the use of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) computer package Version 22.0. The findings of this study may enable coaches to come up with appropriate mechanisms that may help athletes manage their stress effectively. Similarly it may help secondary schools in Kenya institute appropriate interventions to help athletes cope with the stress associated with their sporting careers. The study will also help in building on existing literature related to sources of stress, coping strategies and school based interventions among students athlete in secondary schools. The study will also suggest areas of further research that will create ground for researchers interested in the topic, thus contributing to the expansion of knowledge in the field of counseling psychology. The study established that personality related stress positively influences track performance among athletes in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya. The study recommends that the Ministry of Education in Conjunction with Department of Sports of the Ministry of Social Services should develop Secondary School Sports Policy with Sports Stress Management Guidelines to help manage the emerging sports related stress in Secondary Schools in Kenya. Copies of the policy should be availed in all Secondary Schools in Kenya for use by both Games Masters and Teacher Counsellors ion the Schools. Second, There should be proper arrangements for boosting positive personality related stress to strengthen the observed positive influence on track performance among athletes in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya.

Key Words: *Athletics related stress, Stress Management, Personality Related Stress, Athletics Track Performance.*

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1.0 Introduction

Sources of stress in sports have been identified and several of them appear to be common in most sports, suggesting that there could be a core group of stressors experienced by all athletes. These common stressors are; pressure to perform at a high standard, concerns about training, institution and competition environment, individual's personality, coaches' behaviors and coaching styles, and difficulties balancing sport and non-sport commitments (Lombardo, Tan, Jensen and Anderson, 2005).

In Kenya, Sports are important in educational institutions as it supports academic performance. However, it has been viewed in two different perspectives in schools as far as their contribution to school connectedness is concerned. One perceives sports as having positive effect on student academic performance while others view it as a hindrance to academic success and a waste of students' precious time. Therefore, this duality in the perception of the contribution of sports should be corrected through research findings. Besides, it is important to note that sports can assume other functions other than the traditional function of entertainment and leisure. These functions include; supporting academic objectives, boosting students' self-concept, self-efficacy, affective needs, behavioural needs, social needs, discipline, retention rates among others (Ongonga *et al.*, 2010). Sports are now part of academic curriculum in schools under co-curriculum activities by Kenya Institute of Curriculum Development (KICD, 2000).

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Kenya is known for its athletic prowess, however, its performance is getting threatened and athletes seem to be resorting to unconventional ways of dealing with their stress related problems. Since athletic talent is mainly identified and discovered in secondary school students, this study set out to examine and provide information on student track athletes' stress level and how it influences performance. Athletes in public secondary schools experience stress like other elite athletes. The stress is contributed by different factors which if not addressed may affect their track performance. It is not clear whether personality related stress influences students' athletes on track performance of public secondary school student athletes especially in Nakuru County. This is the research gap that this study was to fill. The hypothesis of the study was stated

as H_{01} : There is no statistically significant influence of personality related stress on student track athletes' performance in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya.

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 Personality Related Stress and Students Athletics Performance

Personality traits also influence how a person reacts to stress. Generally, many people can be classified into either Type A or Type B personality type (Kowalski & Westen, 2005). Those with Type A behavior patterns typically exhibit traits; impatience, ambition, competitiveness, and hostility. This makes this category experience high stress levels especially given the probability that their expectations may not necessarily be achieved contrasted by their ambitious nature. As observed by Kowalski and Westen (2005), type A personality are highly sensitive hence likely to be vulnerable to emotional stress. The proactive nature of this personality also makes them have work related stress. Such individuals become workaholics. They spend much of their time at work place not realizing how that negatively affects their social life. Occasionally they may show some tendencies of floating hostility triggered by minor incidents which cause irritation and exasperation. Individuals that fall under this category are therefore vulnerable to high levels of stress compared to their type B counterparts.

Different factors influence personality aspects. These include gender, social roles, family upbringing, age, genetics and related hormonal features and even person's sport preferences (Mohammadi, 2008). Researches in the field of sport psychology have focused on the different personality traits between athletes and non-athletes. However, none of these researches have studied the differences between athletes and non-athletes using the five-factor personality criterion. Kajtna, Tusak, Baris and Burnik (2004) via the personality five-factor criterion studied the personality of high-risk sport athletes (Alpine mountain climbing, ski, paragliding, white water rafting, mountain biking, motorcycling, ski jumping and extreme skiing) and that of low-risk sport athletes (swimming, track and field, sailing, mountain climbing, Nordic ski, karate and flat water rowing) and found out that high-risk sport athletes gained higher scores in their emotional stability while their scores in such factors as conscientiousness and openness to experiences were lower in comparison with low-risk sport athletes. There was no difference between these two groups. Although the aforementioned research has been carried out using the

five personality factor model, unlike this study it has not focused on the differences between athletes and non-athletes.

Filho, Ribeiro and García (2005) studied the personality traits of Brazilian non-athletes and talented athletes (volleyball, basketball, judo and swimming). The result of their study showed that athletes in four personality traits including lawsuit, health concerns, frankness and irritability had higher scores while in emotional prevention, bad-temper or petulance, rape or affront and impatience received lower scores. Also Besharat's (2007) study indicated that in comparison with team-sport athletes, the individual sport athletes have higher Conscientiousness and self-following while in comparison with the same group have lower agreeableness and sociability. Nikbakhsh (2008), too, showed that professional basketball players whose number of being absent is more than others in sociability, agreeableness, and Conscientiousness have lower scores comparing with other players. In this model the five-factor personality model has been used.

Individuals with type B personality are more relaxed, easygoing and less easily angered (Kowalski & Westen, 2005). Type B individuals relative to Type A are more likely to engage in preventive and less risk related behavior under stress. This suggests that type B behavior may be indirectly linked to wellness. Type B personality is the exact opposite of the Type A. Personality type B do not mind losing, they enjoy the game of win and lose. They are hailed as highly creative, innovative, and reflective and are always thinkers of both the inner and the outer world. Stress levels associated with this category of personality are relatively low compared to that of type A. This is because of the minimal pressure to achieve experienced by this kind of personality (Korotkov, Fraser, Houlihan, Fenwick, McDonald & Fish, 2009).

According to Storch *et al.* (2006) burnout refers to the negative consequences of overwhelming stress, including chronic fatigue commonly referred to as athletic burnout syndrome depression which leads to rapid loss of previously learned skills. Burnout can also result from overtraining, encouraged by overzealous fans, coaches, or the teenagers (Storch, Storch, Killiany & Roberti, 2006). Burnout is considered to be spawned the moment the 'costs' of a sport outweigh its rewards, if the costs are stress induced. Athletes with a mastery focus tend to see things from a wider perspective, gaining the full benefits of practice, and are able to persist in the face of difficulty, thus showing more skill development over the course of a season (Storch, Storch, Killiany & Roberti, 2006).

Barry and Barry (2002) conducted a follow-up study using a larger sample size (N = 40) and broader age range (ages 40 to 75). The results of this study also indicated that an Idealist personality type was negatively related to satisfaction with hearing aids. The authors hypothesized that the excessively optimistic idealists might be dissatisfied as a result of their high expectations. The study also found an additional relationship that had not been significant in the earlier study - the Artisan personality type was positively related to satisfaction with hearing aids. The finding of an additional relationship may be related to the larger sample size and broader age range used in this study. Artisans are daring, adaptable, spontaneous, and artistic.

Although the effects of personality have not been studied in the field of speech language pathology, the effects of personality have been examined in the related field of audiology, particularly with reference to satisfaction with hearing aids. Barry and McCarthy (2001) found that an Idealist personality type, as defined by the Keirsey Four Types Sorter, was negatively related to perceived benefit from hearing aids. Those who are Idealist value their relationships with others, and they trust their intuition when making decisions.

The personality characteristics of optimism and pessimism also have been found to contribute to other health issues. A study was conducted to assess the relationship between the personality characteristics of optimism and pessimism in HIV infection progression (Milam, Richardson, Marks, Kemper, & McCutchan, 2004). The progression of the infection was assessed by examining patients' viral load, which is a measure of virus replication in the blood stream. The results of the study showed that pessimism was associated with higher viral loads at the end of the 12-week program than was optimism, i.e., optimism were related to a slower progression of the infection. Researchers found that highly optimistic patients were more likely to adhere to the treatment program and were least likely to have recently used drugs or cigarettes. Those who were highly pessimistic were less likely to have a healthy diet and more likely to smoke cigarettes. However, these variables did not explain the existing relationship found.

Researchers have sought to explore the notion of an "ideal" athletic personality type (Hoffman, 2013). When comparing performances of successful athletes to unsuccessful athletes there appears to be major differences between these two groups. Are there innate, cognitive differences or personalities that underlie the performances of these groups of athletes? Much inquiry has been applied to this thought and research has been mostly inconclusive. Research has been unable to identify a sound theoretical background as well as consistent research that

supports a distinguishable athletic personality type. Researchers have questioned whether there are distinctive differences in personality types between athletes and non-athlete. Many studies have investigated this claim by comparing athletes from individual sports and team sports (Talyabee, Moghadam & Salimi, 2013), contact athletes and no contact athletes (McKelvie, Lemieux, Stout, 2007) and athletes that are male and female (Malinauskas, Dumciene, Mamkus & Venckunas, 2014) with non-athletes. Researchers have noted some differences between athletes and non-athletes. However, more research is necessary to confirm these findings.

Many studies have investigated whether athletes of different sports vary in personality. In one study, researchers compared individual sport athletes' personalities and team sport athletes' personalities (Ilyasi & Salehian, 2011). Findings demonstrated that individual sport athletes were significantly different than team sport athletes on extraversion, openness to experience and conscientiousness (Ilyasi & Salehian, 2011). Furthermore, individual sport athletes reflected higher scores on all these factors (i.e., extraversion, openness to experience and conscientiousness). Other researchers have studied the differences between individual sport and team sport athletes and have found significant differences but have failed to arrive at similar results (Behzadi, Mohammadpour, Hedayatikatooli & Nourollahi, 2012).

In a similar study, researchers examined psychological risk factors as predictors of injury (Ivarsson & Johnson, 2010). The purpose of the study was to examine the relationship between personality factors, coping variables and stress and injury risk. Participants in the study consisted of 48 soccer players from three different teams. Measurements of the study included the Football Worry Scale, Swedish universities Scales of Personality (SSP), Life Events Survey for Collegiate Athletes (LESCA), Daily Hassles Scale, and Brief COPE. Participants were instructed to complete four out of the five measures at the beginning of the season. Also, the athletes were required to complete the Daily Hassles Scale once a week during the season. Once a player was injured, they were excluded from the weekly test during their rehabilitation. Overall, results of the study indicated that anxiety, stress susceptibility (coping), and trait irritability were significant predictors of injury. However, these strategies can be considered maladaptive if used to avoid the stressor. They are also considered maladaptive if the individual is not willing to invest any effort to overcome the adverse stressor. Self-blame and acceptance can be used to explain the majority of injury occurrences.

2.2 Knowledge Gap

The researcher carried out review of various literatures related to; concept of stress among athletes, athletes' performance in relation to institutional stress and athletes' performance. The critically review showed that there is still need of research to be done on influence of Personality Related Stress on Student Athletes' Track Performance creating a research gap that the current study analyzed influence of Competition Related Stress on Student Athletes' Track Performance in Secondary Schools in Nakuru County, Kenya.

2.3 Theoretical Review

The theoretical aspect of this study is informed by Friedman and Ray Personality Type established in the 1950s in which he described personality types into two namely Type A and Type B. They claimed that a certain type of people, "Type A", were much more likely to have high stress level, than "Type B". Friedman (1996) developed a computer test which was used for descriptions of the types. The procedure for type A/B test consists of ten pairs of sentences. For each pair, you choose which one is closest to describing you. The test takes 2-3 minutes to complete. Lower score show type B while higher scores shows type A.

The theory describes a Type A individual as ambitious, rigidly organized, highly status conscious, can be sensitive, care for other people, are truthful, impatient, always try to help others, take on more than they can handle, want other people to get to the point, proactive, and obsessed with time management. People with Type A personalities are often high-achieving "workaholics" who multi-task, push themselves with deadlines, and hate both delays and ambivalence (Friedman, 1996). Friedman suggests that Type A behavior is expressed in three major symptoms: free-floating hostility, which can be triggered by even minor incidents; time urgency and impatience, which causes irritation and exasperation usually described as being "short-fused"; and a competitive drive, which causes stress and an achievement-driven mentality. The first of these symptoms is believed to be covert and therefore less observable, while the other two are overt (Friedman, 1996).

The theory describes Type B individuals as a contrast to those with Type A personalities. People with Type B personality generally live at a lower stress level and typically work steadily, enjoy

achievement and are not stressed when they do not achieve. When faced with competition, they do not mind losing and either enjoy the game or back down. They may be creative and enjoy exploring ideas and concepts. They are often reflective, thinking about the outer and inner worlds. Furthermore, Type B personalities may have a poor sense of time schedule and can be predominately right brained thinkers (Friedman, 1996).

Personality types, Type A, are predisposed to negative health outcomes (*e.g.*, heart disease, stroke, and cancer) associated with stress (Grant & Langanfox, 2003). Individuals with Type A tend to be intense, irritable, highly competitive, socially isolated from others, ambitious, achievement oriented and impatient. Individuals with Type A personalities share a number of common traits found in those scoring high in neuroticism (*e.g.*, anxious, intense, etc.), suggesting that there is overlap between neuroticism as a personality dimension and Type A personality. For instance, it has been reported that neuroticism is positively associated with emotion-focused strategies of defensive coping and that this creates social isolation from others as the person draws into themselves (Penley & Tomaka, 2001). If the social isolation observed in Type A personality, is the result of the same emotion-focused strategies used by people scoring high on neuroticism, then it suggests that neuroticism may be the trait dimension underlying the patterns of Type A personalities (Penley & Tomaka, 2001). This line of inquiry merits further investigation.

2.4 Conceptual Framework

Figure 1 Influence of Competition Related Stress on Student Athletes' Track Performance

Figure 1 indicates the relationship between independent, moderating and dependent variables. The independent variable was institutional stress. Affecting this process is the moderating variable was motivation by Games Teachers. These factors can moderate the relationship between independent variables and dependent variable. The model as conceptualized in this study emphasizes on how the independent variables may influence the dependent variables. The study hypothesizes that unmanaged school based stressors is disastrous to athletics by influence their tack performance.

3.0 Research Design

This study undertook an exploratory survey approach with ex-post facto design. *Ex post facto* research, by its very design, investigates the world as it naturally occurs and explores phenomena that have already occurred (Johnson & Christensen, 2008). The study targeted 3,584 form two and three students in schools with high performance in athletics.

Given the sample size of 351 as per Krejcie & Morgan (1970) sampling table, the following formula was used to calculate stratified sample;

$$ss = \frac{zp}{tp} Xs$$

Where ss – stratified sample, zp –zonal population, tp – target population and s – sample. The sample size distribution for the study is shown in Table 2. The study purposively picked 5 athlete coaches and 5 Teacher Counselors as key informants to give deeper insight into selected stress factors influencing track performance of Student Athletes. The researcher took half of the sample size to represent both the gender in order to analyze how the different gender responds to stress.

Table 1 Sample Size of Student Athletes in School in Nakuru County

Zone	No. Schools	Total No. of Form		Male Athletes	Female Athletes
		2 and 3 Students	Sample Size		
A	4	430	42	21	21
B	6	620	61	30	30
C	3	664	65	33	32
D	4	820	80	40	40
E	7	1050	103	52	51

Total	24	3584	351	176	175
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The study used a structured questionnaire to collect primary data. Descriptive (frequencies and percentages) analysis and inferential statistics such as chi-square test and Pearson's correlation analyses were used to analyze data after appropriate data coding. Descriptive statistics were used to investigate or explore one variable at a time. To test the hypotheses, chi-square test and Pearson's correlation analyses were conducted for each hypothesis and the results interpreted leading to the rejection or acceptance of the null hypotheses stated earlier. All hypotheses was tested at $\alpha=.05$.

4.0 Findings and Discussions

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

Table 1 :Distribution of Responses on Personality Related Stress

Personality Related Stress	1	2	3	4	5
I am a disorganized person.	164(48.2%)	136(40%)	14(4.1%)	8(2.4%)	18(5.3%)
I don't have a hobby and/or participate in social or recreational activities.	136(40%)	128(37.6%)	38(11.2%)	12(3.5%)	26(7.6%)
I react badly to all types of failure and criticism.	66(19.4%)	94(27.6%)	62(18.2%)	22(6.5%)	96(28.2%)
I am a hasty person and I frequently get angry at other people.	104(30.6%)	114(33.5%)	40(11.8%)	30(8.8%)	52(15.3%)
I use non-prescription, mind-altering substances, e.g., caffeine, nicotine, alcohol, cannabis, cocaine, etc., to try and cope.	246(72.4%)	46(13.5%)	22(6.5%)	12(3.5%)	14(4.1%)
I am trapped by undesirable circumstances that I just have to live with.	102(30%)	104(30.6%)	54(15.9%)	54(15.9%)	26(7.6%)
I do not understand why I do the things which I do.	96(28.2%)	126(37.1%)	46(13.5%)	32(9.4%)	40(11.8%)
I have financial obligations which	98(28.8%)	92(27.1%)	82(24.1%)	38(11.2%)	30(8.8%)

I just can't seem to meet					
I do not know what I want out of life.	186(54.7%)	64(18.8%)	38(11.2%)	20(5.9%)	32(9.4%)
I do not feel good about myself and no matter how successful still feel empty.	154(45.3%)	108(31.8%)	38(11.2%)	12(3.5%)	28(8.2%)
I tend to have a very negative outlook on life.	144(42.4%)	106(31.2%)	40(11.8%)	26(7.6%)	24(7.1%)
I do not feel good about myself and no matter how successful I am still feel empty.	124(36.5%)	122(35.9%)	30(8.8%)	30(8.8%)	34(10%)
I do not get along very well with other people and I have few friends.	118(34.7%)	110(32.4%)	52(15.3%)	42(12.4%)	18(5.3%)
I am embarrassed to ask for help when I need it and I find it difficult to accept encouragement and support from others.	112(32.9%)	116(34.1%)	34(10%)	44(12.9%)	34(10%)
I blame other people for my mistakes.	130(38.2%)	110(32.4%)	48(14.1%)	16(4.7%)	36(10.6%)
I worry about things which I cannot change and which do not seem to bother other persons.	130(32.4%)	110(31.8%)	48(10.6%)	16(7.6%)	36(17.6%)
I find it difficult to experience joy, happiness or pleasure	120(35.3%)	116(34.1%)	50(14.7%)	14(4.1%)	40(11.8%)
I find it difficult to forgive myself or others.	102(30%)	106(31.2%)	42(12.4%)	16(4.7%)	74(21.8%)

Data presented in Table 13 indicates that 164(48.2%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement '*I am a disorganized person*' while 136(40%) disagreed; 14(4.1%) were undecided; 8(2.4%) agreed and 18(5.3%) completely agreed with the statement. Similarly, 136(40%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement '*I don't have a hobby and/or participate in social or recreational activities*' while 128(37.6%) disagreed; 38(11.2%) were

undecided; 12(3.5%) agreed and 26(7.6%) completely agreed with the statement. It was also observed that 66(19.4%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement '*I react badly to all types of failure and criticism*' while 94(27.6%) disagreed; 62(18.2%) were undecided; 22(6.5%) agreed and 96(28.2%) completely agreed with the statement. Concerning the statement: '*I am a hasty person and I frequently get angry at other people*' it was observed that 104(30.6%) completely disagreed; 114(33.5%) disagreed; 40(11.8%) were undecided; 30(8.8%) agreed and 52(15.3%) completely agreed. Similarly, 246(72.4%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement '*I use non-prescription, mind-altering substances, e.g., caffeine, nicotine, alcohol, cannabis, cocaine, etc., to try and cope*' while 46(13.5%) disagreed; 22(6.5%) were undecided; 12(3.5%) agreed and 14(4.1%) completely agreed with the statement. It was also observed that 102(30%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement '*I am trapped by undesirable circumstances that I just have to live with*' while 104(30.6%) disagreed; 54(15.9%) were undecided; 54(15.9%) agreed and 26(7.6%) completely agreed with the statement.

With regard to the statement: '*I do not understand why I do the things which I do*' it was observed that 96(28.2%) completely disagreed; 126(37.1%) disagreed; 46(13.5%) were undecided; 32(9.4%) agreed and 40(11.8%) completely agreed. It was observed that 98(28.8%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement '*I have financial obligations which I just can't seem to meet*' while 92(27.1%) disagreed; 82(24.1%) were undecided; 38(11.2%) agreed and 30(8.8%) completely agreed with the statement. Similarly, 186(54.7%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement '*I do not know what I want out of life*' while 64(18.8%) disagreed; 38(11.2%) were undecided; 20(5.9%) agreed and 32(9.4%) completely agreed with the statement. It was also observed that 154(45.3%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement '*I do not feel good about myself and no matter how successful still feel empty*' while 108(31.8%) disagreed; 38(11.2%) were undecided; 12(3.5%) agreed and 28(8.2%) completely agreed with the statement. Concerning the statement: '*I tend to have a very negative outlook on life*' it was observed that 144(42.4%) completely disagreed; 106(31.2%) disagreed; 40(11.8%) were undecided; 26(7.6%) agreed and 24(7.1%) completely agreed. Similarly, 124(36.5%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement '*I do not feel good about myself and no matter how successful I am still feel empty*' while 122(35.9%) disagreed; 30(8.8%) were undecided; 30(8.8%) agreed and 34(10%) completely agreed with the statement.

It was also observed that 118(34.7%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement '*I do not get along very well with other people and I have few friends*' while 110(32.4%) disagreed; 52(15.3%) were undecided; 42(12.4%) agreed and 18(5.3%) completely agreed with the statement. With regard to the statement: '*I am embarrassed to ask for help when I need it and I find it difficult to accept encouragement and support from others*' it was observed that 112(32.9%) completely disagreed; 116(34.1%) disagreed; 34(10%) were undecided; 44(12.9%) agreed and 34(10%) completely agreed.

Similarly, 130(38.2%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement '*I blame other people for my mistakes*' while 110(32.4%) disagreed; 48(14.1%) were undecided; 16(4.7%) agreed and 36(10.6%) completely agreed with the statement. It was also observed that 130(32.4%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement '*I worry about things which I cannot change and which do not seem to bother other persons*' while 110(31.8%) disagreed; 48(10.6%) were undecided; 16(7.6%) agreed and 36(17.6%) completely agreed with the statement.

With regard to the statement: '*I find it difficult to experience joy, happiness or pleasure*' it was observed that 120(35.3%) completely disagreed; 116(34.1%) disagreed; 50(14.7%) were undecided; 14(4.1%) agreed and 40(11.8%) completely agreed. It was observed that 102(30%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement '*I find it difficult to forgive myself or others*' while 106(31.2%) disagreed; 42(12.4%) were undecided; 16(4.7%) agreed and 74(21.8%) completely agreed with the statement.

The level of personality related stress was conceptualized as a composite variable derived from the averages of non-missing responses on 18 items. The overall averages were divided into 3 categories: Low; Moderate and High. The expected highest score per respondent was 50, and therefore, transition points were $x \leq 30$ for Low; $x \geq 31 \leq 60$ for Moderate and $x \geq 60$ for high levels of completion related stress. The findings of the study are presented on Table 19

Table 2 Distribution of Personality Related Stress Levels

Personality Related Stress	Frequency	Percent
Low	44	12.9
Moderate	292	85.9
High	4	1.2
Total	340	100.0

Data presented in Table 14 indicates that the modal group of respondents presented moderate institutional related stress levels (85.9%) compared to 12.9% of respondents who presented low levels and 1.2% who presented high levels.

Table 3: Distribution of Responses on Athletes Track Performance

Institutional Stress	1	2	3	4	5
I worry quite a bit about what the teachers think of my performance.	40(11.8%)	112(32.9%)	38(11.2%)	36(10.6%)	114(33.5%)
I tend to do lots of planning about how to reach my goals.	48(14.1%)	76(22.4%)	36(10.6%)	26(7.6%)	154(45.3%)
I feel confident that I will play well.	34(10%)	80(23.5%)	70(20.6%)	38(11.2%)	118(34.7%)
When a coach or manager criticizes me, I become upset rather than feel helped.	78(22.9%)	98(28.8%)	60(17.6%)	46(13.5%)	58(17.1%)
It is easy for me to keep distracting thoughts from interfering with something I am watching or listening to.	68(20%)	82(24.1%)	66(19.4%)	64(18.8%)	60(17.6%)
I put a lot of pressure on myself by worrying about how I will perform.	56(16.5%)	96(28.2%)	36(10.6%)	44(12.9%)	108(31.8%)
I set my own performance goals for each practice.	22(6.5%)	74(21.8%)	64(18.8%)	58(17.1%)	122(35.9%)
I don't have to be pushed to practice or play hard; I give 100%.	50(14.7%)	90(26.5%)	38(11.2%)	44(12.9%)	118(34.7%)
If a coach criticizes or yells at me, I correct the mistake without getting upset about it.	56(16.5%)	72(21.2%)	54(15.9%)	46(13.5%)	112(32.9%)
I handle unexpected situations in my sport very well.	56(16.5%)	90(26.5%)	56(16.5%)	56(16.5%)	82(24.1%)
When things are going badly, I tell	58(17.1%)	80(23.5%)	56(16.5%)	48(14.1%)	98(28.8%)

myself to keep calm, and this works for me.					
The more pressure there is during a game, the more I enjoy it.	52(15.3%)	98(28.8%)	48(14.1%)	46(13.5%)	96(28.2%)
While competing, I worry about making mistakes or failing to come through.	82(24.1%)	74(21.8%)	54(15.9%)	60(17.6%)	70(20.6%)
I have my own game plan worked out in my head long before the game begins.	72(21.2%)	80(23.5%)	60(17.6%)	40(11.8%)	88(25.9%)
When I feel myself getting too tense, I can quickly relax my body and calm myself.	60(17.6%)	78(22.9%)	56(16.5%)	54(15.9%)	92(27.1%)
To me, pressure situations are challenges that I welcome.	80(23.5%)	94(27.6%)	46(13.5%)	42(12.4%)	78(22.9%)
I think about and imagine what will happen if I fail.	62(18.2%)	82(24.1%)	64(18.8%)	40(11.8%)	92(27.1%)
I maintain emotional control regardless of how things are going for me.	52(15.3%)	66(19.4%)	46(13.5%)	60(17.6%)	116(34.1%)
It is easy for me to direct my attention and focus on a single object or person.	52(15.3%)	72(21.2%)	46(13.5%)	64(18.8%)	106(31.2%)
When I fail to reach my goals, it makes me try even harder.	50(14.7%)	60(17.6%)	44(12.9%)	52(15.3%)	134(39.4%)
I improve my skills by listening carefully to advice and instruction from coaches and managers.	42(12.4%)	56(16.5%)	38(11.2%)	60(17.6%)	144(42.4%)
I make fewer mistakes when the pressure is on because I concentrate better.	54(15.9%)	88(25.9%)	38(11.2%)	66(19.4%)	94(27.6%)

Data presented in Table 2 indicates that 40(11.8%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement *'I worry quite a bit about what the teachers think of my performance'* while 112(32.9%) disagreed; 38(11.2%) were undecided; 36(10.6%) agreed and 114(33.5%) completely agreed with the statement. Similarly, 48(14.1%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement *'I tend to do lots of planning about how to reach my goals'* while 76(22.4%) disagreed; 36(10.6%) were undecided; 26(7.6%) agreed and 154(45.3%) completely agreed with the statement. It was also observed that 34(10%) of respondents completely disagreed with the

statement 'I feel confident that I will play well' while 80(23.5%) disagreed; 70(20.6%) were undecided; 38(11.2%) agreed and 118(34.7%) completely agreed with the statement. Concerning the statement: *'When a coach or manager criticizes me, I become upset rather than feel helped'* it was observed that 78(22.9%) completely disagreed; 98(28.8%) disagreed; 60(17.6%) were undecided; 46(13.5%) agreed and 58(17.1%) completely agreed. Similarly, 68(20%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement *'It is easy for me to keep distracting thoughts from interfering with something I am watching or listening to'* while 82(24.1%) disagreed; 66(19.4%) were undecided; 64(18.8%) agreed and 60(17.6%) completely agreed with the statement. It was also observed that 56(16.5%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement *'I put a lot of pressure on myself by worrying about how I will perform'* while 96(28.2%) disagreed; 36(10.6%) were undecided; 44(12.9%) agreed and 108(31.8%) completely agreed with the statement. With regard to the statement: *'I set my own performance goals for each practice'* it was observed that 22(6.5%) completely disagreed; 74(21.8%) disagreed; 64(18.8%) were undecided; 58(17.1%) agreed and 122(35.9%) completely agreed. It was observed that 50(14.7%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement *'I don't have to be pushed to practice or play hard; I give 100%'* while 90(26.5%) disagreed; 38(11.2%) were undecided; 44(12.9%) agreed and 118(34.7%) completely agreed with the statement. Similarly, 56(16.5%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement *'If a coach criticizes or yells at me, I correct the mistake without getting upset about it'* while 72(21.2%) disagreed; 54(15.9%) were undecided; 46(13.5%) agreed and 112(32.9%) completely agreed with the statement. It was also observed that 56(16.5%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement *'I handle unexpected situations in my sport very well'* while 90(26.5%) disagreed; 56(16.5%) were undecided; 56(16.5%) agreed and 82(24.1%) completely agreed with the statement. Concerning the statement: *'When things are going badly, I tell myself to keep calm, and this works for me'* it was observed that 58(17.1%) completely disagreed; 80(23.5%) disagreed; 56(16.5%) were undecided; 48(14.1%) agreed and 98(28.8%) completely agreed. Similarly, 52(15.3%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement *'The more pressure there is during a game, the more I enjoy it'* while 98(28.8%) disagreed; 48(14.1%) were undecided; 46(13.5%) agreed and 96(28.2%) completely agreed with the statement. It was also observed that 82(24.1%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement *'While competing, I worry about making mistakes or failing to come through'* while 74(21.8%)

disagreed; 54(15.9%) were undecided; 60(17.6%) agreed and 70(20.6%) completely agreed with the statement. With regard to the statement: *'I have my own game plan worked out in my head long before the game begins'* it was observed that 72(21.2%) completely disagreed; 80(23.5%) disagreed; 60(17.6%) were undecided; 40(11.8%) agreed and 88(25.9%) completely agreed. Similarly, 60(17.6%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement *'When I feel myself getting too tense, I can quickly relax my body and calm myself'* while 78(22.9%) disagreed; 56(16.5%) were undecided; 54(15.9%) agreed and 92(27.1%) completely agreed with the statement. It was also observed that 80(23.5%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement *'To me, pressure situations are challenges that I welcome'* while 94(27.6%) disagreed; 46(13.5%) were undecided; 42(12.4%) agreed and 78(22.9%) completely agreed with the statement. With regard to the statement: *'I think about and imagine what will happen if I fail'* it was observed that 62(18.2%) completely disagreed; 82(24.1%) disagreed; 64(18.8%) were undecided; 40(11.8%) agreed and 92(27.1%) completely agreed. It was observed that 52(15.3%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement *'I maintain emotional control regardless of how things are going for me'* while 66(19.4%) disagreed; 46(13.5%) were undecided; 60(17.6%) agreed and 116(34.1%) completely agreed with the statement.

Similarly, 52(15.3%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement *'It is easy for me to direct my attention and focus on a single object or person'* while 72(21.2%) disagreed; 46(13.5%) were undecided; 64(18.8%) agreed and 106(31.2%) completely agreed with the statement. It was also observed that 50(14.7%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement *'When I fail to reach my goals, it makes me try even harder'* while 60(17.6%) disagreed; 44(12.9%) were undecided; 52(15.3%) agreed and 134(39.4%) completely agreed with the statement. Concerning the statement: *'I improve my skills by listening carefully to advice and instruction from coaches and managers'* it was observed that 42(12.4%) completely disagreed; 56(16.5%) disagreed; 38(11.2%) were undecided; 60(17.6%) agreed and 144(42.4%) completely agreed. Similarly, 54(15.9%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement *'I make fewer mistakes when the pressure is on because I concentrate better'* while 88(25.9%) disagreed; 38(11.2%) were undecided; 66(19.4%) agreed and 94(27.6%) completely agreed with the statement.

The level of institutional related stress was conceptualized as a composite variable derived from the averages of non-missing responses on 22 items. The overall averages were divided into 3 categories: Low; Moderate and High. The expected highest score per respondent was 50, and therefore, transition points were $x \leq 37$ for Low; $x \geq 38 \leq 74$ for Moderate and $x \geq 75$ for high levels of completion related stress. The findings of the study are presented on Table 2

4.2 Inferential Statistics on the Relationship between Personality Related Stress and Athletes' Track Performance

The main objective in the study was to a find out the influence of personality related stress on student athletes' track performance in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya. To achieve this objective the following hypothesis was formulated;

Ho₁: There is no statistically significant influence of personality related stress on student athletes' track performance in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya.

The hypothesis postulated that personality related stress has no significant influence on students' athletes' track performance. To ascertain the truth in the assumption, simple regression analysis of competition related stress on student athletes track performance was done. The results are presented in Tables 4, 5 and 6.

Table 27 indicates that the Pearson Correlation coefficient between personality related stress and students athletes track performance was statistically significant, ($r=0.378$, $p=.000$). The r-square was found to be .143. This indicates that only 14.3% of the variance in student athletes track performance can be explained by personality related stress. Therefore 85.7% of the variance in student athletes track performance was explained by other factors outside this study.

Table 4

Model Summary

Model	r	r Square	Adjusted r Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Sig.
1	.378 ^a	.143	.140	4.715	.000

Table 4 shows the results of simple regression analysis of influence of personality related stress on student athletes' track performance.

Table 5: Simple Regression Analysis of the Influence of Personality Related Stress on Student Athletes' Track Performance

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	1253.325	1	1253.325	56.385	.000 ^b
Residual	7513.087	338	22.228		
Total	8766.412	339			

From Table 5 it can be seen that the F-value was significant ($F(1,338) = 56.385, p=0.000$). This implies that there is a significant influence of personality related stress on student athletes' track performance. Personality related stress factors could be used to predict student athletes' track performance in secondary schools. The null hypothesis H_{04} : There is no statistically significant influence of personality related stress on student athletes' track performance in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya was rejected at 0.05 level of significance. This implies that personality related stress can be used as a predictor of student athletes' track performance in secondary schools.

Table 6 presents regression coefficients between personality related stress and student athletes' track performance.

Table 6: Regression Coefficient of the Influence of Personality Related Stress on Student Athletes' Track Performance

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	12.196	1.373		8.884	.000
Personality Related Stress	5.380	.717	.378	7.509	.000

The results in Table 29 indicated that the beta value was significant ($\beta=.378, p=0.000$). The simple regression model therefore can be used to predict student athletes' track performance from institutional related stress is given by

$$Y = 12.196 + 5.380X_2 + \varepsilon \text{ where;}$$

Y = Student athletes track performance

X_2 = personality related stress

These findings is supported by the output of an experimental research conducted by Morris (2014) that was conducted among undergraduate students where sample size ($n=28$) was selected through convenience sampling. The experimental group was 13 individuals who traveled to Ghana, West Africa to participate in an immersive research project regarding post-traumatic stress disorder. This group consisted of 11 females and two males, with ages ranging from 21 – 50 and a mean age of 28.8. The control group consisted of 15 individuals: 14 females and 1 male, with ages ranging from 20 - 56 and a mean age of 27.8. Using Pearson's Correlation, scores from the Revised Neuroticism-Extraversion-Openness Personality Inventory (NEO-PI-R) were compared to mean Spontaneous Emotional Reactions (SER) scores. The analysis supported hypothesis one, neuroticism and stress were positively correlated, ($r = .51$) participants who scored higher on neuroticism had a significantly higher mean score for SERs. The analysis also supported hypothesis two, showing a significant negative correlation between extraversion and stress ($r = -.44$) participants who scored higher on extraversion had a significantly lower score for SERs. Using an independent samples t-test, overall perceived stress scores were compared for the experimental and control groups. The analysis established that the experimental group had significantly higher overall SER scores than those participants in the control group, ($t = 6.76$).

The study is further supported by Filho, Ribeiro and García (2005) who studied the personality traits of Brazilian non-athletes and talented athletes (volleyball, basketball, judo and swimming). The result of their study showed that athletes in four personality traits including lawsuit, health concerns, frankness and irritability had higher scores while in emotional prevention, bad-temper or petulance, rape or affront and impatience received lower scores.

Other studies that support this finding include; Besharat's (2007) who established that in comparison with team-sport athletes, the individual sport athletes have higher Conscientiousness and self-following while in comparison with the same group have lower agreeableness and sociability. Nikbakhsh (2008), too, showed that professional basketball players whose number of being absent is more than others in sociability, agreeableness, and Conscientiousness have lower

scores comparing with other players. In this model the five-factor personality model has been used.

Another study that support the findings of the current study was carried out by Ivarsson and Johnson (2010) who examined the relationship between personality factors, coping variables and stress and injury risk. Participants in the study consisted of 48 soccer players from three different teams. Measurements of the study included the Football Worry Scale, Swedish universities Scales of Personality (SSP), Life Events Survey for Collegiate Athletes (LESCA), Daily Hassles Scale, and Brief COPE. Participants were instructed to complete four out of the five measures at the beginning of the season. Also, the athletes were required to complete the Daily Hassles Scale once a week during the season. Once a player was injured, they were excluded from the weekly test during their rehabilitation. Overall, results of the study indicated that anxiety, stress susceptibility (coping), and trait irritability were significant predictors of injury. However, these strategies can be considered maladaptive if used to avoid the stressor. They are also considered maladaptive if the individual is not willing to invest any effort to overcome the adverse stressor. Self-blame and acceptance can be used to explain the majority of injury occurrences.

5.0 Conclusions and Recommendations

5.3. Conclusions

The study examined influence of personality related stress influences students' track performance in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya. The study established that personality related stress negatively influences track performance among athletes in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya.

Ho₁: There is no statistically significant influence of personality related stress on student track athletes' performance in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya.

The hypothesis was tested using simple regression analysis. The simple regression analysis showed that;

1. There was a positive relationship between personality related stress and student athletes' track performance in secondary schools ($r = .378$).

2. Personality related stress accounted for 14.3% ($r^2=0.143$) variation in relation to student athletes track performance in secondary schools in Nakuru County.
3. Personality related stress had significant statistical influence ($F(1,338) = 56.385, p=0.000$) students' track performance in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya

5.2 Recommendations

Based on the conclusions of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. There should be proper arrangements for boosting positive personality related stress to strengthen the observed positive influence on track performance among athletes in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya.
2. Guidance and counselling departments should design appropriate programmes for school based interventions promote athletes self image to increase the positive influence on track performance among athletes in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya.

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